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RISK ASSESSMENT BY CLINICAL COURSE AND DIAGNOSIS IN PATIENTS WITH COVID 19 IN A DENTAL INSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

The novel coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak is an international public health emergency. aimed at protecting the public from the unknown risk posed by COVID-19. At the beginning, the epidemic was sufficient reason for health authorities to delay aerosolization procedures and between dental professionals and dental patients. Visits to the dentist. Dental care is a priority, and years of research have proven that there is no professional classification system. Based on these tools, we also recommend measures to help.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; risk assessment; dental care; oral health; dentistry; infection.

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ОЦЕНКА РИСКА ПО КЛИНИЧЕСКОМУ ТЕЧЕНИЮ И ДИАГНОСТИКЕ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С COVID 19 В СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ УЧРЕЖДЕНИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Вспышка нового коронавируса (COVID-19) представляет собой международную чрезвычайную ситуацию в области общественного здравоохранения, направлена на защиту населения от неизвестного риска, связанного с COVID-19. Вначале эпидемия была достаточной причиной для органов здравоохранения, чтобы отложить процедуры aerosolization, а также между стоматологами и стоматологическими пациентами. Посещения стоматолога. Стоматологическая помощь является приоритетом, и годы исследований доказали, что не существует системы профессиональной классификации. Основываясь на этих инструментах, мы также рекомендуем меры, которые помогут.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; оценка рисков; Стоматологическая уход; здоровье ротовой полости; стоматология; инфекционное заболевание.

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COVID 19 BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA STOMATOLOGIYA MUASSASASIDA KLINIK KECHISHI VA TASHHISLASH ORQALI XAVFNI BAHOLASH

ANNOTASIYA

Yangi koronavirus (COVID-19) epidemiyasi jamoat salomatligi uchun xalqaro favqulodda holat hisoblanadi. jamoatchilikni COVID-19 keltirib chiqaradigan noma'lum xavfdan himoya qilishga qaratilgan. Boshida epidemiya, sog'liqni saqlash organlari uchun, aerazol hosil qilish tartiblari va stomatologiya mutaxassislari va stomatologiyadagi bemorlar o'rtasida kechikish uchun etarli asos bo'ldi. Tish shifokoriga tashriflar. Stomatologik parvarish ustuvor hisoblanadi va ko'p yillar davomida tadqiqotlar yo'qligi va ekanligini isbotladi professional tasniflash tizimi. Ushbu vositalarga asoslanib, biz yordam beradigan choralarni ham tavsiya qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; xavf-xatarni baholash; stomatologik parvarish; og'iz bo'shlig'i salomatligi; stomatologiya; infeksiya.

Introduction. The novel coronavirus (COVID-19) epidemic that emerged in December 2019 is an international public health problem. Records from the Center for Systems Science and Engineering, Johns Hopkins University (April 2021) showed more than 149,000,000 cases of COVID-19. with over 3,000,000 deaths worldwide. The data showed that internationally, the United States (USA), India, Brazil, France, Russia, Turkey, and the United Kingdom (UK) are the most affected countries [1,2].

COVID-19 has led to a global health crisis, and of all dental workers, providers are the most affected. Interestingly, many reports have highlighted the risk of dental care due to its proximity to the oral cavity, where high infectious disease is noted. In 2020 as an answer. For this risk, many health authorities in the field of dentistry, including the American Dental Association (ADA) and the World Health Organization (WHO), have called for the elimination of elective dentistry procedures at the beginning of the pandemic. These decisions seemed logical to protect public health [3-8].

A subsequent study in the United States (US) published in the November issue of the Journal of the American Dental Association (2020) found that less than 1% of dentists. The entire country has been tested positive for COVID-19. The ADA respectfully disagreed.

With WHO decisions and based on this research, the ADA restored dental care and recommended the use of the highest level of personal protective equipment available, such as masks, goggles, and face shields. The use of ADA rubber dams and high-speed suction as well as manual metering are recommended to control the risk of aerosol formation.

Materials and methods

1. Using keywords relevant to the study ("COVID-19", "SARS-CoV-2", "Risk Assessment", and "Dental Settings"), we searched for relevant literature published from 2019 to 2021 in two bibliographic databases (PubMed and Web of Science). Using the same thing

period (2019-2021), we searched for published guidelines and recommendations. Official websites of a number of health authorities: the Federal Monitoring Service for the Protection of Consumer Rights and Human Welfare (Russia), the World Health Organization (WHO), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (USA) and the UK Medical Association (Great Britain). Then,

based on the search results, we analyzed the risk of infection with the coronavirus (COVID-19) infection in dental institutions.

2. We have adopted Sechenov University Risk Assessment Criteria (KOR) and Sechenov University. Our previously proposed COVID-19 occupational classification system (Mitrokhin et al., 2021) at the 3rd International Electronic Conference on Environmental Studies and Public Health - Health Issues in the Context of the COVID-19 Pandemic (ECERPH-).

3. Development of an approach to measure the risk of infection of the dental units of the COVID-19 infection.

Results and discussion.

It is possible to estimate the risk of infection with the new coronavirus (COVID-19). Infection using the following sanitary and hygienic risk assessment criteria (KOR): infectious dose (D), number of contacts (n), time (T), distance from the source of infection (H) and screening (M) [26-29].

The magnitude of the risk of infection with COVID-19 can be measured using the following scale: High risk (HR), Medium risk (MR), Low risk (LR). A novel risk assessment method, together with a new occupational classification system, was previously developed at the 3rd International Electronic Conference on Ecology.

Research and Public Health (Mitrokhin et al., 2021) and we believe it is possible to adapt them to measure the risk of infection with the coronavirus (COVID-19) in dental units.

Based on the routes of transmission, several preventive measures should be taken against COVID-19. Studies have shown that the main ways of its spread are the respiratory tract. Droplet and indirect contact, but other routes of vertical transmission have not yet been confirmed.

Aerosol transmission has not yet been confirmed, but should be considered due to high aerosol-generating dental procedures by dental workers [30-32].

Thus, according to the Sechenov University (KRR) risk assessment criteria, the risk of infection of medical workers with COVID-19 is moderate to high. However, implementation

The low risk (LR) criteria in the occupational classification system help to minimize the infectious risk of corona virus (COVID-19) dental care. With the onset of the coronavirus pandemic, many authors and health authorities have proposed different risk assessment tools, and there are differences in assessment criteria. The World Health Organization (WHO), the British Medical Association (BMA), the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), and many public health authorities and authors have proposed risk assessment approaches. Based on these foundations and tools they have, expert opinion and best practices in the professional field of health [33].

This risk assessment has more complex criteria (risk factors): infectious dose, number of contacts, contact time, distance from the source of infection and personal protective equipment.

equipment. Using these criteria, the assessment of the risk of COVID-19 can be more consistent. For healthcare professionals and managing this risk in dental settings [20]

Recommended risk assessment based on the following criteria: age, ethnicity, biological sex, disability, health status, and pregnancy. None of the criteria proposed by the BMA are included here is what we proposed. WHO proposed an approach that includes time, distance and personal protective equipment, but did not consider the infectious dose and amount of contacts [34-36].

Recommendations.

Recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) for healthcare institutions. The World Health Organization (WHO) has published a list of existing and new recommendations to prevent SARS-CoV-2 infection of healthcare workers. Included in this is the creation of an infection prevention and control (IPC) program and the establishment of occupational health and safety programs. It is important to review these guidelines and minimum requirements for health and safety standards structures.

Sorting patients. All asymptomatic patients should be treated the same as people with COVID-19, and all dental procedures should be considered after testing positive for COVID-19.

Avoid procedures that generate aerosols. Dentists should avoid aerosols to best practice their procedures and prioritize the use of hand tools in combination with chemical-mechanical caries

removal tools such as scoop excavators. in addition, if an aerosol-generating procedure is performed, it should be scheduled as the last appointment of the day.

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